

**Convergence between Corruption and the Coronavirus
Pandemic in Brazil**

Összefüggés a korrupció
és a koronavírus-járvány között Brazíliában

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Abstract: In the context of the global pandemic, news platforms have started to play a fundamental role in Brazilian politics. It is in the communication environment that political disputes develop, placing the media in the focus of political disputes for their ability to destroy career policies or conversely, to enhance the democratic development of a country. Therefore, the present work provides a narrative framework for corruption in Brazilian news portals during the first months of the Covid-19 pandemic. The empirical analysis is based on the content analysis of texts published in May in Brazilian newspapers. The objective of the research is to observe how the political dialogue on corruption and the pandemic was translated in the media at a time of crisis in various sectors of the country. It is observed that in this context corruption intersected with the pandemic narrative, displaying three narrative tendencies: as a contributor to government instability, as a way to reinforce the country's crisis, and as a way to increase the perception of corruption.

Keywords: *Brazil, political communication, corruption, Covid-19.*

Összefoglalás: *A globális új típusú koronavírus-járvány kapcsán a híroldalak alapvető szerepet játszanak a brazil Politikai életben. Ebben a kommunikációs környezetben alakulnak ki a politikai viták, és ezeknek a vitáknak a középpontjába kerül maga a média is mint olyan politikai eszköz, mely karriereket tehet tönkre, vagy éppenséggel erősítheti az ország demokratikus fejlődését. Ennélfogva tanulmányomban arra törekszem, hogy narratív keretrendszerrel állítsak fel arról, miként ábrázolták a brazil híroldalak a korrupciót a Covid-19 pandémia első hónapjai alatt. Az empirikus elemzés a brazil újságok május hónapban közölt cikkeinek kritikus forrásvizsgálataán nyugszik. A kutatás célja annak megfigyelése, hogy a korrupcióval és a járvánnyal kapcsolatos politikai diskurzus miként jelenik meg a médiában akkor, amikor az ország különböző szektorai válságban vannak. A kutatás eredményeképpen az látszik, hogy a korrupció és a pandémia kapcsolatáról három narratíva rajzolódik ki: mint ami fokozza a kormányzat instabilitását; mint ami fenntartja az ország válságát; és mint ami növeli a korrupció percepcióját.*

Kulcsszavak: *Brazília, Politikai kommunikáció, korrupció, Covid-19.*

INTRODUCTION

In the face of the Covid-19 pandemic, Brazil stands out in the international arena for facing a crisis not only in its health system but also one in the political and economic realms. The situation in the country is delicate, as a number of factors are contributing to a loss of confidence in the institutions and the instabilities of the state. On the one hand, the country has a high level of infections and deaths. On the other hand, campaigns against social isolation and in favour of the use of hydroxychloroquine were part of the government's narratives.

The Brazilian situation regarding the pandemic is a consequence of a set of political changes that have taken place in the country over the past few years, for example, the public demonstrations in 2013, the impeachment of ex-president Dilma Rousseff (Workers' Party) in 2016, the arrest of former President Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva (Workers' Party), and the election of President Jair Mesias Bolsonaro (without party) in 2018 with 55.13% of the votes.

The 2020 background of the country was one of structural incompatibility, both politically and economically, and a loss of confidence in institutions. In this regard, [Brazilians are facing a lack of structure](#) in the public health system, unemployment, poverty, a lack of public policies and quality education, and especially an awareness of the pandemic.

Even with the growing projection of the number of cases, the Bolsonaro government treated Covid-19 as just a "small flu" (gripezinha), and it encouraged crowding in public spaces and neglected setting up distancing policies. After having participated in several gatherings and not adopting a policy of distancing, in July the President became infected by Covid-19. According to a [G1](#) report, at the time the head of the nation said he was well and reinforced hydroxychloroquine as the cure for the virus.

Together with this, a feeling of insecurity was becoming more and more widespread, as the [government was losing](#) credibility. According to Research Institute [Datafolha](#), Jair Bolsonaro's performance in the coronavirus crisis was approved by 27% in June 2020 and criticized by 49%, and his image was associated with partnership with militants, corruption schemes, fake news, political dispute, dictatorship, authoritarianism, and impeachment. Thus, in the face of the crisis in the country, the media was becoming a source of information for the population, contributing to the construction of the nation's daily narrative.

The importance of this is related to the fact that digital communication platforms are providing a space for political debate during the pandemic. These platforms influence social discussions and consequently decision mechanisms such as voting in an environment where the media is creating mediated visibility, it becomes difficult to control the events published by the media, as the actions are visible. Thus, [media visibility](#) makes a strategy for the stage of daily struggles in the communicational environment, given that in some cases the political scandal represents a decline in the morality of public figures. In this sense, the [media construct political reality](#) through frameworks that highlight political actions, negotiated actions, and political actors.

The new technologies have made it possible to expand the coverage of the private behaviour of political leaders and public figures, allowing [visibility of actions and media](#) that give notoriety to events. Thus, [new technologies](#) make it possible to record private conversations and make them available to thousands of people. Thus, in the globalized age the media makes access to information increasingly viable, especially when dealing with issues such as corruption and politics.

Regarding corruption, according to the [Corruption Perception Index](#), Brazil is ranked 106th out of 180, with a score of 35 out of 100. Regarding corruption, 54% of the population believes that corruption has grown in the last twelve months. According to data from the [Media Freedom Index](#), Brazil occupies 107th place, with a score of 34.05. This shows how corruption is an inherent factor in the country.

With this in mind, this article analyses articles published on Brazilian news platforms as the Covid-19 pandemic hit the country, in order to see what interplay was seen in the media between corruption and the pandemic. Thus, the work provides an overview of the link between corruption and Covid-19. The hypothesis is that in the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, news about corruption in Brazil was published less frequently by the media, and the phenomenon was often relegated to the background of the country's crisis.

Regarding the research corpus, the article uses the content analysis method to translate the materials collected from newspapers and online portals through the NVivo software. This software organizes the information in order to facilitate analyses in qualitative and quantitative research. [Content analysis makes it possible to index](#) and classify the information elements evident in the research. Thus, this method is used here in order to observe how corruption is narrated through the media.

As part of the research, articles published in the news portals of [Veja](#), [Carta Capital](#), and [Brasil de Fato](#) were collected during the month of May 2020. The days chosen for the survey were random, and the news portals were chosen based on the fact that they include a political editorial section. In addition, the chosen communication platforms all have a page rank of 7/10. With a political orientation leaning left and characterized as plural and diversified, *Brasil de Fato* publishes reports on politics, economics, human rights, daily life, and culture, and the page is widely accessible nationwide. Likewise, *Carta Capital* has a progressive bias, leaning to the left. *Veja* occupies a conservative position, with an ideological position to the right.

When discussing cascading corruption news in Brazil, the media reflects influences on voter choices in the face of exposure to information. ["Information cascades may tempt individuals – voters as well as decision makers – to make their choices based on the public sequence of information rather than the quality of this information"](#). Based on this theoretical basis, the present article analyses the link between corruption and the context of the pandemic in Brazil through the media and its construction.

This work contributes to research on corruption at the time of a global pandemic. The article first presents a brief summary of the Brazilian context during the first half of 2020, then it sets out the theoretical basis used for the construction of this empirical research, and finally it presents how the media has narrated corruption in the context of Covid-19.

BRIEF SUMMARY OF THE BRAZILIAN CONTEXT IN THE FACE OF THE PANDEMIC

Corruption scandals have been part of Brazilian life in recent years, drawing attention to the fragility of the country's thirty-year democracy, as corruption generates a series of consequences in the country, one them is [the lack of efficiency in public services](#) and a [lack of confidence](#) in institutions and leaders.

One consequence of the sequences of [corruption scandals](#) is the fall in the confidence of political institutions and a destabilization in the democratic regime. The 2018 Social Confidence Index shows that Brazilian institutions had a low rating when it comes to public confidence (48 points on a scale of 1 to 100), due to the growing distrust of the presidency, political parties, and congress, according to [Ibope data](#). On the other hand, the Social Confidence Index in 2019, according to [Aberje](#), stands at 58 points, 10 points more than that observed in 2018.

The Brazilian situation in the face of Covid-19 is linked to a set of consecutive structural and political changes in the country's history, such as public demonstrations in 2013, the impeachment of ex-president Dilma Rousseff (Workers' Party) in 2016, the arrest of former President Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva (Workers' Party), followed by his release, and a series of scandals and investigations into corruption, such as the *Mensalão* and *Lava Jato* Operations¹.

During his election campaign in 2018, [Bolsonaro presented a proposal to fight corruption](#), stating that if he were elected, in his government there would be no more place for corruption. Today, two years later, corruption is still a recurring factor, which is expanding due to a crisis not only in the health system but also in the political and economic spheres. Highlighting corruption as a problem for [Brazilian democracy](#), the corruption scandals were reflected in the 2018 elections, in which one of the campaign themes was fighting corruption in order to protect democracy and the system of checks and balances.

The month that is in the focus of this research, May 2020, Brazil became one of the countries with the most diagnoses of Covid-19. President Bolsonaro and his followers are opposing the isolation campaigns recommended by the World Health Organization, even being indicted in the [International Criminal Court \(ICC\)](#) by the [Brazilian Association of Lawyers for Democracy \(ABJD\)](#) for crimes against humanity, due to the launch of the "Brazil cannot stop" campaign, which encourages the population to maintain normal daily habits, such as participating in gatherings and allowing the opening of commercial establishments during the Covid-19 outbreak.

1 Mensalão Operation Lava Jato is a set of investigations carried out by the Federal Police of Brazil, which served more than a thousand search and seizure warrants, temporary arrests, preventive detentions, and coercive driving, in an attempt to investigate the money laundering and real scheme in bribes involving politicians and businessmen.

The president referred to the virus as a simple [“small flu”](#) in a national address in the month of April, promoting controversial conduct by supporting social gatherings and the return to routine activities in the country. With the divergence of opinions, from March to May the country had two ministers of health, due to the great pressure in relation to the end of isolation and the impasse between the president, governors, and mayors. At the time, the first Minister of Health, Luiz Henrique Mandetta, opposed the president’s campaign by emphasizing the importance of social isolation in fighting the virus.

The inconsistency deepened days after the second health minister, Nelson Teich, resigned after less than a month in office. As a result, in the middle of the pandemic, the Ministry of Health remained untitled for more than 53 days, until 7 June. According to news portal [R7](#), so far „Bolsonaro has not given any indication that he is looking for a name for the portfolio responsible for facing the pandemic.” Bolsonaro has also been facing a series of demonstrations against his government, and „outside Bolsonaro” demonstrations have occurred in the country’s capitals. In July Vice President Hamilton Mourão in an interview with Globo News said that [„Everything indicates that Bolsonaro will replace Pazuello in Health in ,next moment”](#). This left the question of who was responsible for the position at a critical moment.

In the race to fight the virus, in July the government did a series of tests after the president’s positive Covid-19 test. When disclosing the results during an interview, Bolsonaro took off his mask to make an announcement to journalists, which goes against WHO recommendations. The positive confirmation of the test in conjunction with the President’s negligent behaviour was the target of several international newspapers: [„Bolsonaro, 65, has repeatedly trivialized the pandemic and flouted social distancing, even as Brazil became the second-worst-hit country”](#) and [„Critics at home and abroad have called Mr. Bolsonaro’s handling of the pandemic cavalier and reckless”](#).

For more than three months as interim Minister of Health, on 16 September, General Eduardo Pazuello took over the Ministry of Health, becoming the third occupant of the post in the government. The moment of inauguration was marked by President Jair Bolsonaro displaying a box of hydroxychloroquine to the audience and [referring to himself as ‘Dr. Bolsonaro’](#). According to the Ministry of Health, in the [same month Brazil had approximately 530,480 patients being monitored and 4,060,088 recovered](#).

Regarding his administration during the coronavirus, the President was accused by ex-minister of Justice and Public Security Sergio Moro of interfering in Federal Policy, due to private interests added to incentives. Together with this, Bolsonaro has been accused of radicalizing discourse and promoting dictatorship. In this regard, according to data from research institute [Datafolha](#) released by Folha de São Paulo, 43% of the population considers the Bolsonaro government terrible.

The pandemic in Brazil is surrounded by corruption scandals and games of influence. It is worth remembering that when [dealing with corruption](#), there are different fields of power. The news period of May covers games of influence

involving politicians, businessmen, and the president's family members. Thus, the time period examined in this research portrays news that place corruption at the centre of political schemes or in their background.

According to Transparency International, systemic corruption violates human rights, impeding sustainable development and thus fuelling social exclusion. As [The Global Competitiveness Report, 2016-2017](#) on Brazil points out, the political uncertainty added to a drop in finances tends to prevent the consolidation of the country's competitiveness, one of the largest economies in Latin America and the Caribbean, placing the country in a position of recession.

The media becomes the stage for disputes and, due to the great possibility offered by the information tool, the [media environment](#) soon becomes intense as it generates an increasing volume of publications. The press plays an important role in the investigation and disclosure of [corrupt acts and consequently in promoting anti-corruption policies](#), so in countries with low rates of freedom of the press there is a low possibility of control over those responsible for the power of public opinion.

RESULTS

The research is based on articles published in the political section of three Brazilian communication platforms, *Veja*, *Carta Capital*, and *Brasil de Fato*, during the month of May 2020, during the coronavirus pandemic (Covid-19). The analysis shows that there is a link between the theme of corruption and the pandemic, and the two themes converge in some journalistic materials on these platforms. Three narrative tendencies emerge in which the pandemic and corruption are in dialogue with each other: as a contributing factor to the instability of the government, as a way of reinforcing the country's crisis, and as an instrument that tends to increase the perception of corruption.

In addition, during the analysed period the news were linked to topics such as the change of health ministers, the Covid-19 outbreak, issues related to the Supreme Court, the purchase of health equipment, the imprisonment of ex-president Lula, interfering in Federal Policy investigations, denouncing the president, declarations of interference with the Federal Police, all the while Brazil was becoming the second most infected country in the world.

Based on the material collected and content analysis, a convergence between corruption and the pandemic is clear. With 319 articles analysed, the recurrence of references is as follows: 298 references to the pandemic, 120 to Covid-19, 238 to coronavirus, and 45 to corruption.

A link between pandemic and corruption appears in 15 articles of the 319 articles analysed (Figure 1), where the terms 'corruption', 'pandemic', 'Covid-19' and/or 'coronavirus' are simultaneously mentioned.

Three narrative patterns emerge in these 15 items (Figure 1):

- Corruption combined with the crisis in the health system generated by the pandemic tends to contribute to instability in the government.
- Corruption (new or old cases) before Covid-19 as a tendency to reinforce the country's political and economic crisis.
- Corruption has a tendency to spread in the context of the pandemic.

Figure 1
Corruption and its ramifications in the journal articles surveyed

NARRATIVE PATTERN 1: IN A CONTEXT IN WHICH CORRUPTION IS A RECURRING FACTOR, THE HEALTH SYSTEM CRISIS GENERATED BY THE PANDEMIC TENDS TO CONTRIBUTE TO GOVERNMENT INSTABILITY.

In the articles under analysis the pandemic has contributed to the increased instability of the Bolsonaro government, and in some the idea of impeachment was discussed. Factors such as the population's dissatisfaction with the crisis in the health system and the positions adopted by the government in the face of the pandemic accelerated the president's decline in popularity and also put confidence in institutions in doubt.

Opinion poll data supports this perception of the media narrative. According to data from DataFolha, in early April [59%](#) of the population rejected the President's resignation, as shown by the survey data. At the end of May, this perspective changes, as [48%](#) of the population defends Bolsonaro's resignation, while 50% are against it. Research also shows that the President's disapproval reaches [43% in May](#).

It is worth remembering that one factor contributing to this fall was the president's position against the World Health Organization (WHO). One of the reports linking corruption and the pandemic on a recurring basis is ['Political scientists assess what condition for impeachment is present'](#), published by Veja. The article cites corruption one time, while the pandemic is referred to seven times, and the article focuses on the division of ideas about the probability of the President's departure. The publication presents six political scientists' vision who mention the possibility of President Jair Bolsonaro's impeachment.

The news article compares the crisis generated by Covid-19, its advance, and its consequences for the Bolsonaro government. One of the interviewed scientists mentions the relationship between corruption and the pandemic: "I refer first to the perception of bad management in the pandemic. The importance of this variable will depend on the number of deaths by Covid-19. Second, [the perception that the fight against corruption was fake](#).

Another example of the idea that corruption in conjunction with the pandemic accentuates the crisis in the government is the Veja report ['The canoe and the tripod'](#), which reminds the reader that the President of the Republic is the target of two investigations. The report points out that Bolsonaro made Minister of Justice Sergio Moro reverse an appointment and forced him to replace a Federal Police superintendent, which subsequently caused the former minister to step down. The report clearly makes evident the crisis generated by this accusation, which occurs amidst the high number of Covid-19 infections. As explained in the researched articles, when dealing with government strategies, "To prove that he was an enemy of corruption and to obtain the support of the middle class, the deputy who, in seven terms, belonged to eight different parties, all for hire, adept at low political practices, a friend of militiamen, went to look for Sergio Moro, who embarked in a canoe that should have been stuck".

This news defines Bolsonaro's attitude in the Covid-19 scenario as criminal and catastrophic due to the attacks made by the President on government officials, congress, and the Federal Supreme Court (STF) on a recurring basis. In addition, the report points to the crime of political responsibility in conjunction with the two criminal investigations in which the president is involved. Finally, the report also recalls that Bolsonaro has thirty impeachment requests in progress.

As noted, given the amount of material analysed, there is a fine line which shows the tendency of the government, in the context of the pandemic context, to be related to corruption. It can be concluded that the exposed corruption, added to the pandemic, tends to contribute to the instability of the government.

*NARRATIVE PATTERN 2: WHEN DEALING WITH CASES OF CORRUPTION,
THE CONTEXT OF THE PANDEMIC TENDS TO REINFORCE
THE COUNTRY'S CRISIS CONTEXT.*

Through the survey of the narratives analyzed in some journalistic texts, which deal with corruption and the pandemic, there is a tendency to endorse the crisis in the country, as will be reflected in this section. In general, the media emphasize the idea that even in the crisis scenario generated by Covid-19, corruption is present, as exemplified by phrases such as “in the middle of a pandemic” and “in the midst of a tragic pandemic” inserted in stories about corruption.

One of the political crises addressed by the stories is the fact that the Former Minister of Justice accuses the president of interference in Federal Policy for the purpose of private interests, as it can be noticed in [‘The video speaks for itself’, says Moro on ministerial meeting with Bolsonaro’](#) of Carta Capital.

The report is about the interview with Ex-Minister of Justice Sergio Moro, who claims that the President was not committed to implementing anti-corruption measures and that Moro would have “felt uncomfortable with Bolsonaro’s management, especially in relation to the Police Federal, and spoke about controversial measures taken by the president, such as the change of health ministers amid the coronavirus pandemic”. Thus, the article makes a link between corruption and the pandemic, highlighting the crisis in the Brazilian political system after the denunciation made by ex-minister Sérgio Moro.

It is also worth mentioning that Moro’s departure from the Ministry of Justice is a recurring theme in all reports published in May, mainly due to the politician’s lack of accusation of the president of misconduct and the use of political influence for particular benefits. Moro’s break with the government is characterized by a significant loss of support for the President, considering that the two politicians had had a connection since the 2018 election campaign.

In contrast, the Veja in its report entitled [‘The complaint that puts Wilson Witzel at the centre of a new scandal’](#) describes the investigation that places Wilson Witzel, governor of Rio de Janeiro, at the centre of a corruption scandal. The article explains that the accusation is supported by the fact that the president was previously warned of an operation by the Federal Police in the office of his son, Flávio Bolsonaro.

The main focus of the issue is the relationship between corruption and the pandemic, as the Superior Court of Justice (STJ) received a request to initiate an investigation to ascertain Wilson Witzel’s participation in a corruption scheme which involves building field hospitals and purchasing respirators for coronavirus victims. In terms of corruption, the article points to other terms, such as “embezzlement, bidding fraud, clandestine telephone interception and criminal organization”, in addition to citing the Lava-Jato operation.

Another link between corruption and Covid-19 in the country can be noted in [‘In a virtual trial, TRF-4 maintains Lula’s sentence of 17 years in prison. In the midst of the pandemic, the 8th Panel of the Federal Regional Court of the 4th Re-](#)

[gion \(TRF-4\) maintained the sentence on the Atibaia](#)", from Brasil de Fato. The article resumes the investigation of Operation Car Wash, which has resulted in former President Lula's arrest, accused of passive corruption and money laundering, and for being convicted of being a coordinator and guarantor of a Petrobras corruption scheme. On the arrest of former President Lula, "even without the pandemic, a friend of the ex-president told VEJA that he was practically under house arrest". Thus, the ex-president's virtual judgment is contextualized with the pandemic scenario.

NARRATIVE PATTERN 3: THE CONTEXT OF THE PANDEMIC TENDS TO CONTRIBUTE TO THE INCREASED PERCEPTION OF CORRUPTION.

The final point raised by this research is the trend towards increasing corruption in the Covid-19 situation. The pandemic is contributing to an increase in cases of misuse of public funds and consequently corruption, thus showing a link between the analysed terms.

['Opposition disputes privatization of federal hospitals amid Covid-19 advance'](#) by Brasil de Fato, is an example that deals with the idea of increased corruption, as it informs readers that the federal government has announced the probability of selling *Group Hospitalar Conceição* and *Hospital de Clínicas*, in Porto Alegre. The report claims that the decision disregards the current context by dealing with the privatization of the hospital in the face of a crisis in the health system. Therefore, the article links the pandemic with corruption by recalling that privatization in this sector has favoured corruption: "the deterioration of SUS² and its privatization appear with complete fragility in the pandemic".

Thus, the pandemic seems to have generated a tendency to increase corruption in the country, as observed in the *Veja* report ['The metamorphosis of corruption'](#). With two quotes about the pandemic and three about corruption, the report mentions the reorganization of institutionalized crime during Covid-19.

The article claims that the federal government has promoted the return of the 'centre' to ministries and public offices with the increase of large budgets, and at the same time it states that the Federal Policy maintains gangs linked to the overpricing of equipment used to fight the pandemic. The report also mentions the sixth anniversary of the first arrest during Operation Lava Jato: "in the midst of a tragic pandemic that already kills 1,000 Brazilians a day, institutionalized crime reorganizes and strikes again".

In conclusion, the researched narratives show that corruption in the pandemic tends to increase, due to government manoeuvres related to the purchase of health equipment, field hospitals, and the privatization of the public health sector.

2 Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS): unified health system, i.e. the Brazilian public health system.

CONCLUSION

Using the method of content analysis, it can be noticed that there has been a considerable amount of convergence between the terms 'corruption' and 'pandemic' in the analysed data. Thus, based on the construction of the narrative and the terms collected, it can be concluded that corruption was seen through three lenses in Brazil in the first months of the pandemic : as a contributor to the instability of the government, as a way to reinforce the country's crisis, and as a factor in increasing the perception of corruption.

This link between corruption and the pandemic focused on narratives such as allusion to impeachment, reducing the credibility of the government and institutions, embezzlement of public resources, increased perception of corruption, old and new corruption cases, and political influence.

The tendency to relate the two terms on the analysed platforms allows us to reflect on how the Covid-19 crisis will be reflected in issues related to corruption in Brazil. This raises the question whether the pandemic will be one of the factors that place the country in a wave of instability in the future, thus reinforcing the distrust both in politicians and in institutions. Therefore, this analysis contributes to ways of reflecting on recurrent narratives of corruption in a crisis.